

THE ROLE OF RIGID NASAL ENDOSCOPE IN IDENTIFYING SITES AND CAUSES OF POSTERIOR EPISTAXIS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Epistaxis is among the most frequent emergencies encountered in otorhinolaryngology practice. In many patients, the bleeding source remains unidentified because several regions of the nasal cavity cannot be adequately visualized with routine anterior or posterior rhinoscopy. This limitation highlights the value of rigid nasal endoscopy as a diagnostic tool for evaluating obscure epistaxis. **Aim:** To assess the role of rigid nasal endoscopy in detecting bleeding sites and underlying nasal pathologies in patients presenting with epistaxis when conventional nasal examination fails to determine the cause. **Methods:** A clinical descriptive study was conducted on 100 patients with epistaxis over a one-year period from December 1, 2013, to December 1, 2014, at Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital. Patients older than 13 years whose initial anterior and posterior rhinoscopic examinations were inconclusive underwent rigid nasal endoscopy under local anesthesia to localize the bleeding source and identify associated pathology. **Results:** Posterior epistaxis was more common in males (62%), particularly in middle-aged (33%) and elderly (30%) individuals. Systemic diseases—mainly hypertension (28%)—were frequently associated. Endoscopy identified the posterior septum as the most common bleeding site (43%), followed by the lateral nasal wall (35%), nasopharynx (5%), and floor of the nose (4%). Thirteen percent had no identifiable source. The most frequent endoscopic findings were bleeding points (48%), ulcerations (12%), crustations (11%), and granulation tissue (6%). Notably, 10% of patients had unsuspected benign or malignant nasal masses. **Conclusion:** Rigid nasal endoscopy significantly enhances diagnostic accuracy in epistaxis by precisely localizing bleeding sites and revealing hidden nasal pathologies often missed by routine examination.

KEYWORDS: Epistaxis, rigid nasal endoscope, localization, bleeding points, mass lesions.

INTRODUCTION

Epistaxis is the most frequent emergency encountered in otolaryngology, affecting a substantial proportion of the general population. It is estimated that up to 60% of adult's experience at least one episode of nasal bleeding during their lifetime, although only around 6% require medical intervention, as most cases resolve spontaneously.^[1] Historically, epistaxis has been described since ancient times. The term itself is derived from the Greek *epistazo*, meaning "to bleed from the nose," while early physicians including Hippocrates recognized nose-pinching as an effective method to

control hemorrhage—the earliest recorded form of compression therapy.^[2] Subsequent contributions from scholars such as Al-Tabbari, Morgagni, Kiesselbach, and James Little advanced the understanding of nasal vascular anatomy and bleeding sites, particularly the description of Kiesselbach's plexus as a major source of anterior epistaxis.^[3] Epidemiologically, epistaxis occurs across all age groups, though adolescents and older individuals are more commonly affected.^[4] Younger patients typically present with anterior bleeds, often related to digital trauma or inflammatory conditions, whereas posterior epistaxis is more frequent in adults

over 40 years, frequently associated with hypertension, arteriosclerosis, or vascular fragility.^[5] Environmental factors, including cold weather, low humidity, and seasonal variations in upper respiratory infections, are recognized triggers that contribute to mucosal dryness and subsequent vessel rupture.^[6] Anatomically, the rich vascular supply of the nasal cavity—derived from branches of both the external and internal carotid arteries—underlies the propensity for bleeding. The anterior septum (Little's area) and the posterior-inferior lateral wall (Woodruff's plexus) are particularly vulnerable vascular zones.^[7] Although many episodes of epistaxis are idiopathic, identifiable etiologies include trauma, inflammatory disease, structural abnormalities, systemic coagulopathies, and neoplastic causes.^[8] The clinical importance of epistaxis extends beyond symptom control, as severe cases can result in significant complications such as hypovolemic shock, aspiration, airway compromise, and, rarely, mortality. Effective management therefore requires a structured approach emphasizing initial stabilization, accurate localization of the bleeding source, and progressive therapeutic escalation ranging from topical measures and cautery to packing, arterial ligation, endoscopic interventions, or embolization.^[9,10] In recent decades, rigid nasal endoscopy has transformed the diagnostic and therapeutic landscape. Endoscopic visualization improves detection of bleeding points, particularly in posterior epistaxis, and enhances the precision and success of targeted cautery and sphenopalatine artery ligation.^[11] Aim: To assess the role of rigid nasal endoscopy in detecting bleeding sites and underlying nasal pathologies in patients presenting with epistaxis when conventional nasal examination fails to determine the cause.

METHOD

This clinical descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery at Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital, Baghdad, from 1 December 2013 to 1 December 2014. The study aimed to evaluate the role of rigid nasal endoscopy in identifying local causes of epistaxis.

Study population

A total of 100 consecutive patients were enrolled according to predefined criteria. Inclusion criteria were: age >13 years, either sex, presentation with nasal bleeding (inpatient or outpatient), willingness to provide informed consent for nasal endoscopic examination, and absence of an identifiable cause on anterior and posterior rhinoscopy. Exclusion criteria included patients younger than 13 years (because of difficulty in performing rigid endoscopy under local anaesthesia) and patients who refused consent.

Clinical assessment and initial management

Patients were assessed in the emergency room, operating theatre, or ENT ward, where full resuscitation facilities were available. Initial evaluation included assessment of

consciousness, general appearance (pallor, cold sweaty extremities) and vital signs (pulse, blood pressure). Haemodynamically unstable patients received intravenous fluids and/or blood transfusion as indicated. First priority was control of active bleeding using nasal compression, suction, topical vasoconstrictor-soaked packs (diluted adrenaline or oxymetazoline), and, when necessary, anterior and/or posterior nasal packing.

After stabilization or in patients with inactive bleeding, a structured questionnaire was completed, followed by general and ENT examination. The nose was examined under good illumination after topical anaesthesia and decongestion. Anterior rhinoscopy was performed with a Killian speculum and headlight; posterior rhinoscopy was attempted with a St. Clair–Thompson mirror when feasible.

Nasal endoscopy and investigations

In patients with no identifiable cause on conventional examination, diagnostic rigid nasal endoscopy was performed using 4-mm 0°, 30° and 45° endoscopes (Storz) in a standardized three-pass technique to systematically inspect the inferior meatus, Woodruff's area, middle meatus, sphenopalatine region, sphenoidal recess, and middle meatal complex. Endoscopic findings and bleeding sites were recorded.

When feasible, identified bleeding points were managed endoscopically (chemical cautery with silver nitrate, bipolar/galvanocautery, Gelfoam or miniature targeted packs). Persistent or inaccessible bleeds were treated with conventional anterior and/or posterior packing.

All patients underwent baseline haemoglobin and packed cell volume. Coagulation profile, complete blood count, virology screen, renal and liver function tests, imaging (CT/MRI), and endoscopic biopsy for histopathology were requested selectively based on clinical suspicion, with physician consultation when indicated.

RESULTS

Rigid nasal endoscopy identified a bleeding site in 87% of patients. Posterior septum (43%) and lateral nasal wall (35%) were the main bleeding areas. As in table 1.

Table 1: Endoscopic Sites of Bleeding.

Site of Bleeding	Number of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Nasal septum	43	43%
Lateral nasal wall	35	35%
Floor of nasal cavity	4	4%
Roof of nasal cavity	0	0%
Nasopharynx	5	5%
No identifiable site	13	13%

The most common pathology was active bleeding points (48%), while mass lesions (10%) emphasize the diagnostic value of endoscopy. As in table 2.

Table 2: Pathological Findings Detected by Nasal Endoscopy.

Pathological Finding	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Bleeding points/vessels	48	48%
Ulcerations/erosions	12	12%
Crustations	11	11%
Granulation tissue	6	6%
Mass lesions	10	10%
No pathology detected	13	13%

Severity among active cases: 9 patients (9%) had severe bleeding, while 40 patients (40%) had mild–moderate bleeding. About half the patients presented with active bleeding; severe bleeding occurred in 9%, highlighting the need for rapid endoscopic assessment. As in table 3.

Table 3: Type and Severity of Epistaxis.

Type of Bleeding	Number	Percentage (%)
Active bleeding	49	49%
Inactive bleeding	51	51%

Almost equal right-left distribution indicates the need for full bilateral endoscopic assessment. As in table 4.

Table 4: Side of Bleeding.

Side	Number	Percentage (%)
Right	48	48%
Left	41	41%
Bilateral	11	11%

Hypertension/CVD was the most frequent comorbidity (28%), consistent with known associations with posterior epistaxis. As in table 5.

Table 5: Systemic Comorbidities in Epistaxis Patients.

Systemic Disease	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Hypertension / CVD	28	28%
Diabetes mellitus	13	13%
Chronic renal failure	2	2%
Leukemia	2	2%
Chronic liver failure	1	1%
Wegener's granulomatosis	1	1%
No systemic disease	53	53%

Figure (1): (a) endoscopic view.

Figure (2): showing right nasopharyngeal paraganglioma.

Figure (3): endoscopic view of nasopharyngeal carcinoma.

DISCUSSION

This study confirms that posterior epistaxis is predominantly a disease of middle-aged and elderly patients, with 63% of cases occurring in those ≥ 40 years. This pattern is comparable to Nunez *et al.*, who reported peak incidence in the fifth to seventh decades and attributed it to increased longevity and atherosclerotic vascular change.^[12] The relative paucity of adolescents in our series contrasts with studies that included anterior epistaxis and found higher rates in younger age groups.^[13] This difference is largely explained by our exclusion of patients < 13 years and those with obvious anterior bleeding from Little's area. Male predominance (M:F = 1.6:1) is in keeping with Tomkinson^[14] and Iseh

and Muhammad^[15], and may reflect greater exposure of males to trauma, outdoor work, and environmental hazards, in addition to a possible protective effect of oestrogen on nasal microvasculature in females. Seasonally, the clustering of cases in winter and, to a lesser extent, in hot, dry months mirrors previous reports.^[12,16] Low humidity, heated indoor air and increased upper respiratory tract infections in winter, as well as mucosal dehydration in summer, likely predispose to mucosal cracking and rupture of fragile submucosal vessels.^[6,16] Systemic comorbidities were frequent; hypertension and cardiovascular disease were the most common, echoing several series that identified hypertension as the leading associated medical condition

in epistaxis.^[17] However, our findings support the view that hypertension is more closely related to the severity and persistence of bleeding rather than its initiation, and that elevated blood pressure at presentation may partly reflect anxiety and the stress of admission.^[18,19] Nasal trauma, recent nasal surgery, and anticoagulant use constituted additional important precipitants, consistent with other reports in which trauma and warfarin/ aspirin therapy are major contributors to secondary epistaxis.^[17,20] The principal strength of this study lies in its systematic use of rigid nasal endoscopy after conventional rhinoscopy failed to identify a cause. Endoscopy localized a definite posterior bleeding site in 87% of patients, most commonly the posterior septum (43%) and lateral nasal wall including Woodruff's area (35%), in broad agreement with McGarry, Ritam Ray^[21,22], and allowed detection of significant pathology, including inflammatory polyps, angiofibroma, inverted papilloma, paraganglioma and nasopharyngeal carcinoma.^[22,23] This high diagnostic yield translated into a substantial proportion of patients being managed by direct endoscopic therapy—chemical or electrical cautery and selective packing—rather than blind anterior or posterior packing, supporting the growing consensus that rigid nasal endoscopy should be considered an essential tool in the evaluation and management of posterior epistaxis.^[24,25]

CONCLUSION

Nasal endoscopy offers superior visualization compared to routine rhinoscopy, allowing for the precise localization of bleeding points and hidden pathologies while minimizing trauma from blind instrumentation. Although conventional packing remains essential for stabilizing severe active hemorrhage, endoscopy is the preferred modality for targeted, definitive management.

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